

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL HEADS IN LEADING THE SCHOOLS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INQUIRY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 7

Pages: 643-675

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2291

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13626052

Manuscript Accepted: 08-23-2024

Exploring the Role of Emotional Management of School Heads in Leading the Schools: A Phenomenological Inquiry

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Abstract

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to determine how school heads manage their emotions while leading their schools. This study employed a qualitative method using an in-depth interview among school heads. Key practices identified included maintaining composure, fostering positivity, and promoting collaborative environments. Challenges encountered revolve around navigating the subjective nature of emotions and maintaining focus within the study's scope. However, insights gained underscored the transformative potential of enhancing emotional competence through targeted interventions and ongoing professional development for school heads. This study examined the lived experiences of school heads in managing their emotions while leading their schools, focusing on both personal and professional challenges. School heads shared their strategies for addressing emotional difficulties, highlighting the significance of maintaining composure, practicing emotional intelligence, and fostering open communication to handle diverse personalities and stressful situations effectively. Their methods for emotional regulation included promoting positivity, demonstrating empathy, and encouraging constructive dialogue to cultivate a supportive school environment. The findings indicated that school heads enhanced their leadership effectiveness and improved school climate by embracing diverse perspectives, managing stress, employing conflict-resolution strategies, and fostering motivation and resilience among staff and students.

Keywords: *educational leadership, emotional management, school heads, phenomenological inquiry, purposive sampling, thematic analysis*

Introduction

The ability of school heads to effectively manage emotions is paramount to achieving success in their role as leaders. The inability to control one's emotions can hinder even the most brilliant minds from reaching their goals. Morgan (2021) cited that without sufficient emotional management skills, even knowledgeable people may find success difficult to achieve. This is because developing strong relationships, managing difficult emotions, empathy, and self-awareness are all necessary for effective leadership. Strong emotional management skills in school heads make them more adept at navigating challenging interpersonal situations, motivating, and inspiring others, and fostering a healthy and productive work atmosphere.

In Malaysia, school heads are faced with lots of emotional management issues. Most of them cannot concentrate on their leadership responsibilities due to the stress of overseeing the curriculum and teaching simultaneously. In addition to being overburdened with administrative responsibilities, the lack of rules and incompetence cause problems in performing their jobs and duties. Their motivation is impacted, and emotional management problems result from this kind of situation (Samad et al., 2023). Meanwhile, educational institutions in Bahrain are also under increased pressure to adapt to globalization, and school heads have encountered difficulties in embracing change and preserving comfort. This calls for school heads to have better emotional management skills and stay relevant (Issah, 2018). Also, in China, school heads face challenges concerning the emotional aspects of leadership. The varied needs and goals of stakeholders, their relationships, and their reputations are just a few of the delicate demands that school heads must balance. These demands can be emotionally draining for school heads and place increased pressure on them to actively engage as instructional leaders (Chen & Guo, 2019).

In the Philippines, particularly in the Division of Davao City, school heads in Magsaysay North and South faced a great challenge because they had to hone their leadership abilities and concentrate on determining the course for achieving the institution's goals (Salip & Quines, 2023). School heads concurred that during difficult situations, they had a hard time managing and regulating their emotions as they faced obstacles in their emotionally demanding jobs. They easily get stressed and have trouble handling strong emotions. In line with their efforts to achieve the school's mission, vision, and goals, the entire school community needs to be transformed and propelled to create a positive organizational climate. This requires a certain level of emotional management skills among school heads (Vermeulen et al., 2020).

In the local context, within the Davao de Oro division, I observed that some school heads exhibit poor emotional management skills characterized by insensitivity, dictatorial behavior, and a lack of self-control. This type of ineffective emotional management can have significant and detrimental effects on the overall school environment. When school heads fail to appropriately manage their emotions, it creates an atmosphere of tension and unease within the educational setting. The strained interactions between these school heads, teachers, and students hinder the productive and harmonious functioning of the school community. This not only affects the academic performance of the students but also their emotional well-being.

In my literature reading, numerous studies were conducted about emotional management. A study by Chen and Guo (2018) stated that in times of fast transition, it can be extremely difficult for school heads to control their emotions due to increased pressure and expectations, uncertainty and ambiguity, the emotional impact on others, and their investment and passion. Meanwhile, a study by Pretorius and Plaatjies (2023) looked at the value of self-awareness as a core emotional management competency for school heads' leadership development. However, I have not come across any research that explores the role of the emotional management of school heads in leading public elementary and secondary schools and in addressing the value of social-emotional development in education, including how to create healthy relationships, make responsible decisions, and effectively resolve conflicts. As a result, my motivation to complete the investigation increased.

Consequently, this study is important for understanding how emotional management impacts school leadership. The findings will have practical implications for developing and refining school heads' emotional management skills, thereby informing policy and instructional practices. By uncovering effective strategies for managing their own emotions and those of others, the study aims to provide actionable insights that can help school heads create a supportive environment conducive to learners' overall development and achievement. The findings of this study on school heads' emotional management will be disseminated through publication, school-based workshops, and presentations. This multi-faceted approach aims to reach a wide range of stakeholders and maximize the impact of the research. Thus, this study is open for submission to national and international research conferences.

Research Questions

The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore and understand how school heads' emotional management affects their ability to lead the schools. Furthermore, this study investigated the roles and experiences of public elementary and secondary school heads in the Division of Davao de Oro in managing their emotions.

At this stage of research, the role of emotional management of school heads in leading the schools refers to the lived experiences, obstacles, or limits that school heads meet in leading the schools. This also includes the coping strategies and realizations gained by school heads in employing emotional management in school leadership.

1. What are the lived experiences of school heads on managing emotion as they lead their schools?
2. How do the school heads cope with the challenges they encounter in managing their emotions as they lead their schools?
3. What are the insights of school heads on emotional management that can be shared with others?

Methodology

This section deals with the methodological steps that will be used to gather the data relevant to research problems. This outlines the research design, research participants, role of the researcher, data sources, data collection procedure, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological method in a qualitative research design. Bhandari (2023) defined qualitative research as an all-encompassing methodology that involves the collection and analysis of non-numerical data, such as text, audio, or video, to comprehend concepts, ideas, or experiences. It can also be utilized to gain additional knowledge about an issue or generate fresh concepts for research.

Moreover, this study was qualitative since it explored and understood the role of emotional management in the daily experiences of school heads, providing valuable insights to inform leadership development programs and enhance the quality of educational leadership and management practices. Also, interviews, particularly in-depth interviews, were employed to acquire the information required to respond to the research questions.

Furthermore, a qualitative research method called phenomenology aims to explain and describe a phenomenon or event from the viewpoint of those who have personally experienced it (Tenny, 2022b). The main purpose of this method is to comprehend the feelings and experiences of a specific audience about the nature of the specific phenomena (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). Consequently, the goal of this method is to describe the meaning of an event by considering both what is observed and the way it is experienced (Teherani et al., 2020).

Participants

The participants of this study were 10 school heads from different schools throughout the Davao de Oro Division. Phenomenological research may have one to twenty participants, depending on the period, according to Alhazmi and Kaufmann's (2022) calculation of the study's participant count. Furthermore, according to them, the quantity of participants is not the focus. Instead, the emphasis ought to be on the diversity of the participants and their level of involvement. In addition, the participants were fairly selected and identified through purposive sampling.

Purposive sampling is a technique for identifying and choosing circumstances that will make efficient use of limited research resources.

It will be used to select respondents who are most likely to provide acceptable and useful information (Campbell et al., 2020). A further justification for using a purposive sample technique rather than generalizing findings to the entire population is that qualitative research, particularly phenomenological inquiry, aims to gain insights and delve deeply into understudied phenomena (Alhazmi & Kaufmann, 2022).

The following were the selection criteria that were used in identifying and selecting the participants; (a) those who are designated as school heads or principals both in elementary and secondary schools in the Division of Davao de Oro; (b) those who have led schools for a minimum of three (3) years; (c) those who have rendered at least 30 teaching and non-teaching personnel; and (d) those who are willing to engage in in-depth interviews. Furthermore, I ensured that the participants in this study would vary in age, gender, and school category. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria were based on the following parameters: (a) individuals who do not hold the official position of school head or principal in the Division of Davao de Oro; (b) those who have led schools for less than three (3) years; (c) those who have rendered less than 30 teaching and non-teaching personnel; and (d) those who are not willing to engage in in-depth interviews.

Procedure

Data collection is a methodical process of obtaining measurements or information. It enables researchers to acquire firsthand information and a variety of viewpoints on the research issue (Bhandari, 2021). In qualitative research, data are gathered in an unstructured, flexible manner. Additionally, because qualitative researchers have a close relationship with the participants' natural surroundings, they will serve as the main research instruments for data collection and analysis (Clark & Veale, 2018). The following methods, which are required for data collection, will be employed in this study:

First, I secured approval from St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc.'s Research Ethics Committee (REC) to carry out the study. Once approval has been granted, I asked the Dean of Graduate School Education for an endorsement letter, which will act as permission to carry out the study. I need to ask for permission to make sure that the actions I take to gather data or information from participants are appropriately approved and allowed by these relevant authorities.

Second, I sent the endorsement letter from the Dean of Graduate School Education, together with my research proposal, to the link provided by the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro to formally request permission to conduct the study in the said division. Because this is a phenomenon that is exclusive to schools, consent from the superintendent is necessary. The authorized permission document explaining that the study has been approved by a higher authority will then be given to the selected participants.

Third, participants who met the pre-determined selection criteria were contacted and extended an official invitation to take part voluntarily. I secured consent from the participants through an Informed Consent Form (ICF). Before conducting an in-depth interview, an Informed Consent Form was sent and retrieved personally from the participant. I conducted a 25-minute orientation with the participants at their most convenient time to discuss the purpose of the study.

Fourth, I created and prepared the interview guide myself, which was then verified by experts. I gathered data from the in-depth interviews with the participants face-to-face. Before the interviews, I reminded the participants about the impending in-depth interviews along with the notes they needed to prepare for the interview. I conducted interviews with the participants following the timetable we have mutually agreed upon and their availability; the interview will not exceed an hour. To make sure that their answers were accurately captured and not altered or misinterpreted, I used a voice recorder when conducting the interview. The Informed Consent Form would be their approval in allowing me to record the entire duration of the interview and take some notes from their responses to have a verbatim transcription of their responses and avoid misinterpretation of the provided data. In addition, before the interview, I made sure that they were in a comfortable location that was away from noise and distractions so that they could directly express their thoughts and experiences.

Fifth, in the interview, I asked them questions about their experiences in employing emotional management practices and the insight they had gained from their experiences. They were free to discuss and respond using local language during the interview. Any questions from them were accepted and answered respectfully. I asked follow-up questions to augment and enhance the information to be taken from them. Moreover, courtesy was observed throughout the whole interview process. After the interview, I read my written notes based on their answers to every question in the interview guide, and I let them make corrections to avoid misleading information. I gave them digital copies of transcriptions for them to check, review, delete, and make modifications to their responses.

Finally, a thorough recording of everything that happened during the interviews was made and saved on the computer in preparation for transcription. All the recorded files were stored in a password-protected folder using a password-protected computer to ensure the safety of the file, and hard copies of materials were stored in a locked cabinet. A password was used to secure the collected data, and only the researcher, research adviser, and data analyst could access it. After gathering and transcribing the participant accounts, I started the data analysis procedure. Furthermore, the gathered data will be destroyed after 3 years. Also, the participants were given a copy of the Data Privacy Notice, and the notice was signed and returned to the researcher.

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics is the practice of conducting research in a way that is both morally and legally acceptable. These comprise guidelines that describe appropriate and inappropriate conduct in addition to right and wrong (Resnik, 2020). To make sure that all research ethics guidelines are followed, this study was presented to the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. Additionally, in this study, 10 dimensions of ethical considerations were strictly observed, including social value, informed consent, vulnerability of the research participants, risks, benefits, and safety, privacy and confidentiality, justice, transparency, qualification of the researcher, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

Social Value. Research with human subjects must be both scientifically and socially valuable to adhere to the notion of social value. Otherwise, it would be unreasonable to subject research participants to the dangers and negative effects of studies that cannot yield valuable information or directly benefit them. In addition, the demand for social value encourages prudent resource management and lowers waste throughout the research sector (Kerasidou & Binik, 2022).

In this research, its worth was dependent on sociological relevance. The primary aim of this study was to broaden our comprehension of the emotional management that school heads need to effectively lead their schools. It may also help guide policies, interventions, and training initiatives that attempt to enhance school leadership, which would benefit teachers, students, and the educational system as a whole. In addition to serving as a guide for future research projects with a similar focus, the study's findings may be used to inform policy recommendations and to develop appropriate, need-based, and research-based leadership programs for school heads in the Department of Education (DepEd) Region XI.

Informed Consent. Informed consent is a fundamental research ethics principle that states that to engage in a study, participants must give their free, informed, and continuous consent. Getting informed consent in qualitative research entails educating participants about the objectives, procedures, potential benefits and downsides, and their rights. In addition, participants ought to be allowed to ask questions and exit the study whenever they like (Rana et al., 2023).

In this study, it is essential to uphold the concept of informed consent. Research participants received a thorough explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, possible risks, and benefits before their involvement. It is best to acquire informed consent willingly, making sure that participants are aware of their rights, given the opportunity to ask questions, and are free to stop participating at any moment without repercussions. This suggests that the participants are free to disclose or withhold from the researcher any information they desire.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The National Bioethics Advisory Commission (NBAC) suggested in its 2001 report Ethical and Policy Issues in Research Involving Human Participants that vulnerability in research should be interpreted as a condition of some individuals, either inherent or situational, that increases the likelihood that they will be used in unethical ways (Gordon, 2020). Likewise, vulnerability is a key concept in research ethics since it helps identify research participants who should be given special consideration because their participation in the study puts them at a higher risk of harm (Lajoie et al., 2020).

In this study, participants were regarded as vulnerable due to the potential emotional influence of the interview questions. However, as the researcher, I ensured that there was no unpleasant language in the interview schedule or the questionnaires. Additionally, it was emphasized that participants may opt-out at any moment or continue engaging.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety. Risks are the potential hazards that the study participants may encounter in the conduct of the study (Enago Academy, 2023). The term "benefit" refers to both the measurable advancement of knowledge, our economy, people, and society, as well as the positive impacts that the research has on those interested in the research, such as participants (UK Research and Innovation, 2023). As for their safety, participants have the right to be free from pain and injury as well as to be protected from exploitation, as stated by Barrow et al. (2022), under the Belmont Report's concept of beneficence.

Before conducting the study, I got the participants' consent and explained to them its goal, including any risks, benefits, and safety measures. I also guarantee that they would not be forced to participate in the study and that they will be protected because there is a potential that they could be threatened or manipulated into doing so. To lessen risks and ensure participants' security, the in-depth interview will take place at a time that works best for them. To ensure that the guide questions used in the administration of the interview won't cause too much harm, they will be first validated by experts. Also, no confidential or sensitive queries will be asked; the questionnaire's sole purpose is to gather data for the study. I will be extremely cautious when gathering data to ensure that private and unnecessary information is excluded. Each participant will also receive a token as a thank you for their time and work. These tokens express appreciation while highlighting the significance of their impact on the creation of educational policies and procedures.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Researchers must guarantee participant confidentiality and data privacy and retain data in line with the Data Privacy Act. Documents should be stored in a secure area, and data should only be available to the researcher and other team members (Mirza et al., 2023). Furthermore, the researcher believes that the confidentiality of people and their privacy should be maintained. As a result, participant consent is needed before disclosing any personal information, and it must be kept confidential (Hassan, 2024).

Justice. Justice is often understood to mean treating people in a way that is appropriate, fair, and equitable (Varkey, 2021). Further,

justice is to make sure that the costs, advantages, and dangers of taking part in research projects are distributed fairly and equally.

In this study, I observed fairness by using the right sampling technique in choosing the participants. The study was carried out in an acceptable setting with suitable resources and skills, and it will be done so with the utmost rigor and expertise. In addition, I treated the participants fairly, regardless of their position or level within the institution.

Transparency. Moravcsik (2019) discussed that there is an agreement in research transparency that researchers have an ethical responsibility to make their evidence, analysis, and research design publicly available to assist in the evaluation of their knowledge claims based on evidence. Being transparent means needing to make available the information, analysis, procedures, and interpreting decisions that support one's assertions in a manner that enables others to evaluate them. Also, Steltenpohl et al. (2023) stated that the sharing of data, materials, and coding schemes is typically at the center of transparency arguments, especially when it comes to repeatability. Transparency and integrity are enhanced when researchers explain their history and role, considering their impact on the study process and data interpretation.

In this study, transparency was regarded as an essential element. This helped the participants understand that the main goal of the study was to ascertain how school heads' emotional management impacts their capability to lead their institutions. The participants were informed of their active involvement in the data collection phase through individual, in-depth interviews. The participants were informed of the procedure's potential hazards and discomforts. Giving participants access to the study results was an additional ethical concern that needs to be considered.

Qualification of the Researcher. A good researcher should possess the following ten attributes, according to Acmc (2021): precision, receptivity, enthusiasm, endurance, carefulness, expertise, impartiality in his research, passion, approachability, and the capacity to function under pressure.

My research adviser, who is more informed about the subject of research, served as my guide in this study. I chose to move forward with this investigation because I think I possess the necessary knowledge to carry out the analysis, have developed a strict strategy, and expect insightful outcomes. This shows that I am aware of the limitations of my research expertise and have the abilities and knowledge required to complete the specific study.

Adequacy of Facilities. Abubakar (2023) indicates that the proper utilization and availability of equipment and facilities are positively correlated with improved performance and results. Buba et al. (2023) narrated that there are three distinct concepts to consider: accessibility, adequacy, and availability regarding educational facilities.

In this study, I guaranteed that all the materials needed for this research were easily obtainable. Books, internet journals, and unpublished dissertations can all be used as further readings and sources. I also knew that the cameras, audio recorders, and other gear required to complete the study were easily accessible. I also asked the appropriate offices and groups for their permission. This suggested that, given the availability of facilities, supplies, and suitable communication, there was a guarantee that I would be able to carry out and finish the study.

Community Involvement. In research, community involvement describes the cooperation between higher education institutions and their broader communities (local, state, region, country, or world) for mutually advantageous information and resource exchange in a cooperative and reciprocal environment (Tamban et al., 2020).

Before conducting this study, I asked permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro to carry out the study. Participants were provided with all the information required for them to participate in the research's future results. Since the research findings may develop strategies and interventions to raise school heads' emotional management, active participation in the study was essential. In the meantime, the study's findings were shared with both internal and external stakeholders to provide knowledge and increase awareness.

Results

This section presents the findings of the study on how school heads manage emotions while leading their schools. Insights were gathered from in-depth interviews and meticulously analyzed, and core ideas were extracted with guidance from the research adviser. Key themes were identified and synthesized from these transcriptions, illustrating the detailed experiences of school heads in managing emotions as they lead their schools.

Lived Experiences of School Heads on Managing Emotion as They Lead Their Schools

The first question asked was, "What are the lived experiences of school heads in managing their emotions while leading their schools?" Most participants shared their insights and experiences related to emotional management. They talked about their personal and emotional challenges while carrying out their school responsibilities. Therefore, after analyzing the data collected from the interview of the participants regarding their experiences in managing emotions while leading their schools, five (5) key themes emerged, namely: (1) Managing Emotions in Difficult Situations; (2) Staying Positive to Enhance Morale and Happy Disposition; (3) Building Strong Relationships and Promoting Productivity; (4) Maintaining Open Communication; and (5) Inability to Handle Own Emotions.

Table 1 shows the major themes and core ideas on the lived experiences of school heads on managing emotion as they lead their schools.

Table 1. *Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Lived Experiences of School Heads on Managing Emotion as They Lead Their Schools*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Managing Emotions in Difficult Situations	regulating one's emotions to attain favorable results in tense circumstances exerting emotional restraint in making decisions mastering the ability to handle diverse personalities having a high emotional quotient in managing anger maintaining emotional control to make sure everyone feels comfortable maintaining composure and using peaceful means of resolving conflicts striking a balance between ideas and feelings being able to show appreciation and recognition
Staying Positive to Enhance Morale and Happy Disposition	fostering happiness by serving being considerate of the valid reasons of others looking for an alternative scheme promoting fair treatment and understanding designing effective answers to problems
Building Strong Relationships and Promoting Productivity	showing greater support for teachers and letting them work collaboratively sharing best practices and solicit comments fostering empathy and professionalism fostering a positive outlook in life
Maintaining Open Communication	expressing emotion healthily and constructively listening and encouraging open communication showing good relationships with teachers and other personnel in the school
Inability to Handle Own Emotions	others do not fully understand your good intention having trouble adjusting to individual differences challenges in balancing authority

Managing Emotions in Difficult Situations

School heads often face the challenge of managing their emotions to attain favorable results in difficult circumstances. They demonstrated emotional restraint in making decisions and mastered the ability to handle diverse personalities, ensuring that everyone felt comfortable. They practiced emotional intelligence and balanced their ideas and feelings by using peaceful means to resolve conflicts and demonstrate respect for others.

IDI-01 emphasized the importance of regulating the emotion, as she shared:

"I have to regulate my emotion, suko na kaayo ko and that I have to control my emotions kay it seems na they do not like my idea, but ... I have nothing to do but to go down, stop and wait for a while"

(I had to regulate my emotions. If I am very angry, I need to control my emotions because it seemed they did not like my idea. But I had nothing to do but to step back, stop, and wait for a while.)

IDI-04 also added,

"as a leader, exerting emotional restraint in making decisions is needed especially sa mga times nga suko or pungot na kayo ta tungod sa mga negative nga situations"

(as a leader, exerting emotional restraint in making decisions is needed, especially during times when we are very angry or frustrated due to negative situations)

IDI-04 also emphasized the importance of handling diverse personalities, she shared:

"individual differences of teachers is difficult to handle kay lahi lahi gyud ang matag individual with different emotional needs and responses"

(individual differences among teachers were difficult to handle because each person has unique emotional needs and responses)

IDI-10 also shared:

"given na gyud na sa mga school head na biggest challenge was mastering the ability to handle diverse personalities, especially when daling with difficult parents, and students with behavioral issues"

(the biggest challenge for school heads was mastering the ability to handle diverse personalities, especially when dealing with difficult parents and students with behavioral issues)

In addition, IDI-02 highlighted the importance of having a high emotional quotient in managing anger, she shared:

"definitely dapat, mayroon kang emotional quotient at tsaka, yung intelligence quotient, and then of course in leading, it is also very important na mataas yung emotional quotient mo. As a school head, you may get frustrated with teachers who are late or fail to submit reports on time."

(definitely, having an emotional quotient and an intelligence quotient was essential. In leadership, having a high emotional quotient is also very important. As a school head, you might be frustrated with teachers who were late or failed to submit reports on time)

IDI-10 also added:

"para sa akoo, I maintain emotional control into daily interactions by practicing active listening and empathy. Tapos as a school head, gina encourage pud nako ang tanan for open communication and create opportunities for staff and students to express their feelings"

(for me, I always maintain emotional control in daily interactions by practicing active listening and empathy. It was crucial to encourage open communication and create opportunities for staff and students to express their feelings)

In the same vein, IDI-03 also shared:

"I demonstrated emotional control through respect for the opinions of others kay naay uban na ma misinterpret ta nila kay pagtuo nila wala nato gi respect ilang opinions"

(I demonstrated emotional control through respect for the opinions of others because some people might misinterpret our actions as not respecting their opinions)

In addition, IDI-10 also shared:

"sa kadugayon nako sa service, naa gyud daghang mga challenges, apil na deraa ang pag maintain og composure and avoiding conflict under stressful circumstances sa time nga mo interact or mo coordinate ta with learners and teachers. Maka sugat gyud ta anang mga academic and emotional issues and I managed these problems gyud professionally and compassionately"

(in my years of service, there were indeed many challenges, including maintaining composure and avoiding conflict under stressful circumstances when interacting or coordinating with learners and teachers. Academic and emotional issues could really affect, and I managed these problems professionally and compassionately)

Similarly, IDI-08 emphasized the need for peaceful means in resolving conflicts, she shared:

"ang akong positive experience in managing my emotion in leading the school kay I think using peaceful means of resolving conflicts, kana bitaw dili ko magpakita na nasuko ko pag-ayo, I need to show teachers and some respect, commitment and passion in leading the school"

(my positive experience in managing emotions while leading the school was using peaceful means of resolving conflicts. I do not show my anger to teachers; instead, I show respect to them and maintain commitment and passion for leading the school.

IDI-01 also added:

"as a school head, naga apply kog emotional management kay through anang striking a balance between sa akong emotions and pang huna-huna. Kay naay mga problems nga need nako ma address carefully by considering other reactions and interactions"

(as a school head, I applied emotional management by striking a balance between my emotions and ideas. Some problems needed careful resolution by considering other reactions and interactions)

In summary, school heads consistently emphasized the importance of managing emotions to handle conflicts within their schools effectively. They highlighted the need to regulate their emotions, particularly during moments of frustration or anger, by maintaining composure and using peaceful means to resolve disputes, as it helps in maintaining effective decision-making and handling diverse personalities. They also navigated challenges professionally and compassionately, which created a positive atmosphere for both staff and students.

Staying Positive to Enhance Morale and Happy Disposition

Optimistic dealings enhanced morale and fostered a happy disposition among school staff and students. By showing appreciation and recognition, school heads boosted confidence and motivation. They also fostered happiness by serving others and considering their valid reasons.

IDI-04 shared the importance of appreciation and recognition in motivating stakeholders; she shared:

"kailangan nato ang appreciation and recognition because it will help them nga mas maging motivated to work hard for the good sa atong school. Example ani, kay during PTA meeting, gina invite nato ang barangay official para makit an sa mga teachers and parents ang ilang support, so in that way napakita nako ang appreciation and recognition of their effort para sa kaayohan og kalamboan sa

school”

(we needed appreciation and recognition because it helped them become more motivated to work hard for the good of our school. For example, during PTA meetings, we invited barangay officials to show teachers and parents their support. In that way, I demonstrated appreciation and recognition of their efforts for the benefit and progress of the school)

IDI-08 also shared:

"if kabalo ta magpakita og appreciation and recognition, mas matagaan pa nato sila og chance na maningkamot pa gyud sa pag solve sa mga problems within the school. Unya through pud ana nu, mas naka build kog strong relationships with the community because it helps them become committed sa pag offer sa ilang support here sa school"

(if we knew how to show appreciation and recognition, we could give them more chances to continue striving to solve problems within the school. And through that, I also built strong relationships with the community because it helped them become committed to offering their support here at the school.)

In the same vein, IDI-09 added:

"ang akong positive experience in managing my emotions in leading the school was to foster happiness by serving. Kailangan nako na paglingkuran ang mga clients, ilabina sa mga teachers and learners"

(my positive experience in managing my emotions while leading the school was fostering happiness by serving. I needed to serve the clients, especially the teachers and learners)

In addition, IDI-04 highlighted the importance of allowing others to be happy by the act of serving, she shared:

"for example, during sa meeting, gina tagaan nako og chance ang mga teachers to fostered happiness by serving, same anang dapat tagaan nato sila og role like sila ang mohatag og introduction, or maging masters of ceremony pag naay program. As a school head, maging gaan nlang ang tanang boluhaton sa school kung maging happy ta through serving them"

(for example, during meetings, I allowed teachers to foster happiness by serving, such as assigning them roles like giving the introduction or being the masters of ceremony during programs. As a school head, all the tasks at school became easier when we were happy through serving them)

IDI-02 also added:

"definitely, kailangan gyud nato maging considerate of the valid reasons of other teachers. Parehas anang mananghid sila na moabsent usa kay nasakit ilang anak or naay mga family problems na need e solve"

(definitely, we needed to consider the valid reasons of other teachers. For example, when they asked for permission to be absent because their child was sick or they had family problems that needed to be solved)

IDI-03 also shared:

"we needed to be considerate of the valid reasons of others kay wala ta kabalo if unsa na gyud ka stressful ilang situation. Atleast man lang as a school head napakita nako sa ilaha that I cared for them. Unya mas ganahan papud mag work si teacher kung considerate ta sa ilang mga hangyo sa time nga lisod kaayo ilang kahimtang"

(we needed to consider the valid reasons of others because we did not know how stressful their situation was. At least as a school head, I showed them that I cared for them. Also, teachers were more willing to work when we were considerate of their requests during difficult times)

In connection, IDI-05 also added:

"when I am at school, kailangan dili nako ginapakita nga suko gyud kaayo ko, I need to look for an alternative scheme especially when I'm mad"

(when I was at school, I needed to avoid showing that I was outraged. I had to look for an alternative scheme, especially when I was mad)

In addition, IDI-06 also shared:

"kailangan nato makakita og alternative scheme para dili mosamot og ka negative ang situation. Parehas anang pag mokalit rag absent si teacher unya siya ang master of ceremony sa program within that day. So instead nga ma stress ta kailangan gyud ta mangita og alternative scheme or sulbad para dili ta masamot ka stress sa situation"

(we needed to find an alternative scheme to prevent the situation from becoming more negative. For example, when a teacher suddenly called in sick, they were supposed to be the master of ceremonies for the program that day. Instead of getting stressed, we needed to find an alternative scheme or solution to avoid becoming more stressed by the situation)

IDI-07 shared the importance of promoting fair treatment and understanding; she said:

"kanang naga promote ra gyud kog fair treatment and understanding unya mas nakasabot ko sa ilang situation og tungod pud ani naka offer ko sa ilaha og effective solutions to problems. Naka build pud ni siya og strong relationships sa mga tao kay mas na feel man nila nga ginapahalagan nako sila by being fair and understanding"

(I promoted fair treatment and understanding and better understood their situations. Because of this, I offered them effective solutions to problems. This also built strong relationships with people because they felt valued by my being fair and understanding)

In the same vein, IDI-09 also shared:

"promoting fair treatment and understanding kay need gyud siya og wisdom in managing our reactions and interactions sa uban. Kay usahay baya abi nako ng nakahatag kog fair treatment sa uban pero lahi diay sila og pagsabot, unya na feel na dayon nila nga mas gitagaan og consideration ang uban kaysa sa ilaha"

(promoting fair treatment and understanding required wisdom in managing our reactions and interactions with others. Sometimes, I thought I had given fair treatment to everyone, but they understood it differently and felt that others were given more consideration than them)

In summary, the school heads highlighted the importance of appreciation, recognition, and fostering happiness through service in motivating their stakeholders. They also emphasized considering valid reasons for the absences of teachers and looking for alternative schemes to prevent negative situations from escalating.

Building Strong Relationships and Promoting Productivity

Building strong relationships and promoting productivity were crucial for creating a supportive and efficient work environment. Designing effective answers to problems, showing greater teacher support, and encouraging collaboration enhanced overall productivity.

IDI-03 shared the steps she made in designing an effective answer to problems, she said:

"as a school head, naga design gyud kog steps sa paghatag og effective answers to problems. Example ani nga mga problems kay mentally unstable ang teachers tungod sa daghang problema sa family unya madungagan pa gyud derea sa school"

(as a school head, I took steps to design effective answers to problems. For example, there were issues where teachers were mentally unstable due to many family problems, which were compounded by additional challenges at school)

IDI-08 also added:

"nakabalo gyud ko mag design og mga effective answers to problems related to emotional stress, specially sa akong kaugalingon nga dali ra kaau ko masuko gyud, unya usahay wala ko'y patience sa mga bagay bagay. Mao ni nu, ang akong pagka school head gyud ang hinungdan nga nag mature gyud ko emotionally"

(I knew how to design effective answers to problems related to emotional stress, especially since I easily got angry and sometimes lacked patience. This experience as a school head was what led me to mature emotionally)

In the same vein, IDI-04 also shared:

"kanang nakita nako nga ang usa ka teacher kay murag naa siya'y pag alinlangan sa iyang skills, dili siya confident, I always showed him or her greater support man gyud and I also let them work collaboratively"

(when I saw that a teacher seemed unsure of their skills and lacked confidence, I always showed them greater support and encouraged them to work collaboratively)

In connection, IDI-06 also added:

"katong nag start nako og pakita og greater support for teachers and let them work collaboratively nakahatag gyud siya og nindot nga impact sa akong leadership kay mas nagging positive gyud ang pag approach sa teachers sa tanang mga tasks here sa school and also naka help siya na dili bitaw ko ma tawag as an angry administrator"

(when I started showing greater support for teachers and letting them work collaboratively, it positively impacted my leadership. It made the approach to all tasks at school more positive and also helped prevent me from being labeled as an angry administrator)

In the same vein, IDI-01 also shared:

"I shared best practices and solicited comments to the output of others. Gina applied namo na derea sa school specially during LAC session or even during PTA meeting, pag naay mga nindot nga discoveries si teacher nga maka help sa pag grow sa school, they were allowed to share their best practices and even solicited comments to the importance of such project to the learners"

(I shared best practices and solicited feedback on the outputs from others. We applied this at the school, especially during LAC sessions or PTA meetings. When teachers made valuable discoveries that could help the school's growth, they could share their best practices and receive comments on the importance of such projects for the learners.)

IDI-02 highlighted the importance of sharing best practices and soliciting comments, she shared:

"isa gyud sa problem nu kay ang uban malain gyud na sila samot na og dili nako paminawon ilang mga ideas or mga possible solutions sa problems. Dili gyud na bag-o sa akoo as school head, nga dili gyud tanan positive atong madunggan sa ilahan pero effective gyud nga gina allowed gihapon nako na mag shared sa ilang best practices and also they were encourage to solicit comments about sa negative or positive sides ana nga mga solutions"

(one problem was that some people became upset, especially when I did not listen to their ideas or possible solutions to problems. As a school head, it was not new to me that not everything I heard from them was positive, but it was effective in allowing them to share their best practices. They were also encouraged to solicit feedback about the negative or positive aspects of those solutions)

IDI-06 also added:

"natun-an nako ang paghatag og empathy and professionalism in leading the school, gamit kaayo ni siya specially pag naay time nga ang mga teachers naa sila'y personal problems. Dili gyud na malikayan nga naay mga teacher nga magkabikil gyud tungod sa ilang lahi lahi nga prinsipyo"

(I learned to give empathy and professionalism in leading the school, which was especially useful during times when teachers had personal problems. It was unavoidable that there were teachers who had conflicts due to their differing principles)

IDI-09 also added:

"based sa akong experience, ginapakita nako ang empathy and professionalism sa pagsulbad sa mga problems related to emotional management. Example ani kay last time nag cramming na gyud tanang teachers sa kadaghan og reports na need e submit unya nag practice pa gyud na sila sa mga bata for graduation. So ako as school head, instead nga akong padali dalion ang teachers na maka submit, mas gipili nko nga sabton usa ilang ka busy"

(based on my experience, I demonstrated empathy and professionalism in solving problems related to emotional management. For example, there was a time when all the teachers were cramming due to numerous reports that needed to be submitted and preparing students for graduation. As the school head, instead of rushing the teachers to submit their work, I chose first to understand how busy they were)

In summary, school heads actively took steps to address problems related to emotional stress and management by demonstrating empathy and professionalism. They supported teachers facing personal and professional challenges, encouraged collaboration, and shared best practices while soliciting feedback. These approaches not only improved their leadership effectiveness but also fostered a more positive working environment within the school.

Maintaining Open Communication

Maintaining open communication significantly enhanced the overall school environment by fostering a positive outlook and improving interpersonal relationships. School heads could model effective communication and encourage a culture of openness by expressing emotions healthily and constructively. This approach strengthened relationships with teachers and other personnel and created a supportive atmosphere that facilitated better teamwork and mutual respect.

IDI-03 shared the importance of having a positive outlook in life when faced with challenges, she said:

"as a school head, of course I fostered a positive outlook in life in which naka helped siya para mas ma appreciate pa ang effort na akong gibuhat para sa school. Kay lisod baya kaau mag lead sa school unya feeling nako if nega pako sa kinabuhi, super na gyud ka stressful na"

(as a school head, I naturally fostered a positive outlook on life, which helped others appreciate the efforts I made for the school. Leading a school was already challenging, and I felt that if I had a negative attitude, it would have made everything even more stressful)

In connection, IDI-04 also added:

"simple ra gyud, kailangan naa ta'y positive outlook in life kay sa akoo bitaw experienced if sige ratag huna huna nga dili gyud nato masulbad ang problem, mas mosamot gyud kalisod ang sitwasyon, so akoang ginabuhat is to think positive nga kaya gyud nako akong responsibility as school leader"

(we needed to have a positive outlook on life. From my experience, the situation would only become more difficult if we constantly thought that a problem was unsolvable. So, what I did was to think positively and believe that I could handle my responsibilities as a school leader)

IDI-06 highlighted the importance of expressing emotions healthily and constructively; she shared:

“when you are at school, you need to express your emotion healthily and constructively samot na og suko na kaayo ka sa imong co-teacher. In my experienced katong nagkatubag mi sa isa ka teacher kay tungod wala niya nagampanan ang iyang mga responsibilities as adviser unya I need to confront him na kailangan tagaan og chance ang ubang teacher na maging adviser pud, so sap ag explain nako para dili siya ma hurt, naningkamot gyud kog express healthily and constructively”

(when you are at school, you must express your emotions healthily and constructively, especially when you are very upset with a co-teacher. In my experience, when I had to address a teacher who had not fulfilled their responsibilities as an adviser and needed to explain that other teachers should be given a chance to be advisers as well, I made a conscious effort to communicate healthily and constructively to avoid hurting them)

IDI-01 also added:

“I mean kailangan nimo e express imong emotion healthily and constructively to balance your decision and also para mas masabtan pud nila nga need pud diay nila mag improve. But I made sure that I am correcting them positively nga dili sila malain”

(I meant that you needed to express your emotions healthily and constructively to balance your decisions and help them understand that they also needed to improve. I made sure to correct them positively so that they would not be upset)

In the same vein, IDI-03 emphasized the need for listening and open communication in the workplace, she shared:

“we cannot please everyone pero kailangan gyud nato na ang listening and encouraging open communication para naay peacefulness sa workplace kay ako as a leader dili man pud ko perfect gud, maka commit pud kog mistake”

(we could not please everyone, but listening and encouraging open communication was essential to maintain peace in the workplace. As a leader, I was not perfect and also made mistakes)

IDI-07 also shared:

“by listening and encouraging open communication mas masabtan nato why and how things happen unya naka help pud siya na ako as a school leader maging fair ko sa pag resolve sa conflict especially sa pag correct sa mga lapses sa ubang teacher. Dili na siya pa hawd hawd, kundi ang gusto lang gyud nako mas mag improve pa sila professionally, so in doing that I applied listening and encouraged them to openly communicate what they felt”

(by listening and encouraging open communication, we better understood why and how things happened, which also helped me, as a school leader, to be fair in resolving conflicts, especially when correcting lapses from other teachers. It was not about being stern but rather aimed at helping them improve professionally, so I applied listening and encouraged them to communicate their feelings openly)

In the same vein, IDI-06 shared the importance of showing good relationships with teachers and other personnel, she said:

“benefits of showing good relationships with teachers and other personnel in the school kay mas maging healthy ang relationship sa mga kaubanan unya dili pud mataha or magtanom og kalain ang uban sa imoha”

(the benefits of showing good relationships with teachers and other personnel in the school were that it made the relationships healthier and prevented others from having grudges or negative feelings towards me)

In addition, IDI-05 also shared:

“as a school head, kailangan gyud nato magpakita og good relationships with teachers and other personnel in the school para mas daghan pa og mobuhat na kalamboan unya dili pud gubot. Parehas derea sa school kanang amigo man mi tanan so makita gyud na siya by having a good relationship with teachers and other personnel”

(as a school head, it was essential to show good relationships with teachers and other personnel in the school to foster more progress and avoid conflicts. For example, at our school, we were all friends, which demonstrated the benefits of maintaining good relationships with teachers and other staff)

In summary, school heads emphasized that maintaining a positive outlook and expressing emotions in a healthy way were crucial for effective leadership and conflict resolution. They highlighted that listening and encouraging open communication were essential for understanding situations, ensuring fairness, and preventing misunderstandings and grievances.

Inability to Handle Own Emotions

School heads highlighted that solving the challenges of emotions and those of others might be difficult to adjust. They also encountered situations where their good intentions were misunderstood by others, causing strain in communication and relationships.

IDI-01 shared that others did not understand her good intentions, she said:

“yes, nag exist gyud na siya kay maski unsaon nato dili man ta perfect as school head, naa gyud na that they do not fully understand

your good intention, especially kanang naa ka'y project e proposed na maka help sa mga bata unya need man gyud mo submit og documents para ma approved, mao na magreklamo napud ang ubang teachers kay dagdag napud sa ilang trabahuon pero ang imoha lang gyud as school head nga makahatag ka og kaayohan para sa tanan"

(yes, it existed because, no matter what we did, we were not perfect as school heads. There were times when others did not fully understand our good intentions, especially when we proposed projects intended to benefit the students but required submitting additional documents for approval. As a result, some teachers complained about the added workload, even though our main goal was to provide benefits for everyone)

IDI-02 also added:

"this is very hard that others do not fully understand my good intention kay maka caused gyud siya og conflict and tsismis sa ubang teachers. Nahitabo baya ni sa akua last time kay kini bitaw derea sa school, duol man gyud ni og kalsada so nag proposed ko ato nga dili lang derea e agi ang samintado nga dalan kay dilikado kaayo sa mga bata kay bali natungan man gud ang kalsada sa school buildings. Unya na misinterpret na dayon ko sa mga tao, pagtuo nila wala ko nipirma na derea e agi ang kalsada, gibuhatan kog issue nga ako daw rason nganong hangtod karun wala pa na start og ayos ang kalsada na sementado"

(it was challenging when others did not fully understand my good intentions, as it led to conflicts and gossip among the teachers. This happened to me before when I proposed that the road adjacent to the school should not be used for heavy traffic because it was dangerous for the students, given that the road was directly next to the school buildings. However, people misinterpreted my suggestion, believing that I was the reason the road repairs had not started yet, and made it an issue by accusing me of causing the delay)

IDI-04 also shared her difficulty of adjusting to individual differences, she shared:

"the first for me is having trouble adjusting to individual differences kay lahi lahi gyud ang matag individual with different emotional needs and responses, so for me, lisod kayo e apply ang one size fits all, because the decision that I made with my 30 other teachers and vice versa"

(for me, the first challenge was having trouble adjusting to individual differences, as each person had unique emotional needs and responses. Applying a "one size fits all" approach was very difficult because the decisions I made had to consider the diverse needs of my 30 teachers and vice versa)

In the same vein, IDI-03 also shared:

"naa gyud na ayy nagkaproblema gyud ko unsaon pag adjust to individual differences. Lahi lahi man gud og pagsabot matag tao, naay uban na ma misinterpret ta nila kay pagtuo nila wala nato gi respect ilang decisions"

(I did experience problems adjusting to individual differences. People had varying understandings, and some might misinterpret our actions, believing that we did not respect their decisions)

In addition, IDI-06 shared the challenges she encountered in balancing authority, she said:

"ang other challenge is unsaon pag find a balance with authority. For example, I imposed authority even when there is habitual absences or even absences of the teachers due to illnesses"

(the other challenge is on how to find a balance with authority. For example, I imposed authority even when there is habitual absences or even absences of the teachers due to illnesses)

In connection, IDI-07 also shared:

"I always find a balance with my authority by knowing the real situation, why does it happen"

(I always find a balance with my authority by knowing the real situation, and why it happens)

In summary, school heads encountered significant challenges when their good intentions were misunderstood, leading to conflicts and gossip among staff. They struggled with adjusting to individual differences, as each person had unique emotional needs and responses, making a uniform approach difficult. They also found it challenging to balance authority with empathy, particularly in cases like habitual absences.

Coping Strategies in Facing the Challenges Encountered in Managing Emotion as they Lead Their Schools

In response to the second question, "How do school heads cope with the challenges they encounter in managing their emotions as they lead their schools?" most participants talked about their coping strategies. They shared various approaches to managing their emotions and described how support from individuals and organizations helped them. Additionally, they explained how their attitudes and perspectives played a crucial role in helping them navigate emotional challenges while leading their schools. As the participants discussed their methods and strategies for managing emotions while leading their schools, their responses revealed distinct patterns in the transcriptions. The data analysis identified four (4) key themes that emerged from their experiences, namely: (1) Emotional

Enhancement and Resilience Building; (2) Fostering Open Communication; (3) Maintaining Self Composure and Optimism; and (4) Reduced Stress and Enhanced Motivation.

Table 2 shows the major themes and core ideas on coping strategies of school heads in managing their emotions as they lead their schools.

Table 2. *Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Coping Strategies of School Heads in Facing the Challenges Encountered in Managing Emotion as They Lead their Schools*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Emotional Enhancement and Resilience Building	cultivating resilience fostering transparency embracing diverse perspectives utilizing conflict-resolution strategies reflecting on emotions before deciding
Fostering Open Communication	giving thoughtful responses engaging in leadership training embracing diversity and acceptance managing emotions to prevent hurtful situations
Maintaining Self Composure and Optimism	fostering positivity staying composed in high-pressure situations finding time to relax when feeling very happy or mad mitigating stress through open communication
Reduced Stress and Enhanced Motivation	practicing self-reflection to manage stress fostering compassion

Emotional Enhancement and Resilience Building

Emotional enhancement and resilience building were central to the experiences of school heads as they navigated the complexities of leadership. Cultivating resilience allowed them to face challenges positively while fostering transparency ensured that their intentions and decisions were clearly understood. Embracing diverse perspectives and utilizing conflict-resolution strategies further enabled them to manage interpersonal relationships effectively and maintain a constructive school environment.

IDI-08 shared the importance of cultivating resilience, she said:

"pag feel nako nga ma burn-out nako, I always cultivated resilience by teaching myself sa pag adapt sa mga stressors"

(when I felt I was on the brink of burnout, I always cultivated resilience by teaching myself to adapt to stressors)

In the same vein, IDI-07 emphasized the importance of transparency in her leadership, she shared:

"I fostered transparency sa akong mga kaubanan aron makasabot sila if unsa ang mga problems nga need e resolve sa institution. Akoa gyud na gina emphasized sa ilaha nga as one gyud mi derea"

(I fostered transparency with my colleagues so they would understand the problems that needed to be resolved within the institution. I emphasized to them that we were all in this together.)

In addition, IDI-04 also shared:

"so for me, I'm on a transparent type of leadership. Kanang naga practice pud gyud ko anang dapat maging open ta sa mga bagay bagay ilabina sa mga teachers, students, and parents, and also keeping them informed about the school policies, the school decisions and changes"

(so, for me, I practiced a transparent type of leadership. I made sure to be open about various matters, especially with teachers, students, and parents, and kept them informed about school policies, decisions, and changes)

IDI-02 also shared the importance of embracing diverse perspectives with other people, she shared:

"sa pud nga akoang gina practice and pag embraced sa diverse perspectives sa mga tao nga part sa school. That was helpful for me samot na kay people have different personalities different experiences, different backgrounds and because of that, kailangan e accept mo talaga at tanggapin mo na in a leadership part talaga yang tinatawag natin embracing diverse perspectives"

(I also practiced and embraced diverse perspectives among the people in the school. This was helpful for me, especially since people have different personalities, experiences, and backgrounds. Because of this, it was essential to accept and recognize that embracing diverse perspectives is a crucial part of leadership.)

In addition, IDI-04 also shared:

"of course, you have to embraced diverse perspectives to every member of the school community. Sa tanang teachers, the parents, as

well as the learners, dapat ma feel nila ang comfortability in expressing their own selves, their own emotions and concern“

(I had to embrace diverse perspectives for every school community member. All the teachers, parents, and learners needed to feel comfortable expressing their selves, emotions, and concerns)

In connection, IDI-06 emphasized the importance of utilizing conflict resolution strategies, she said:

“I overcome things by utilizing conflict-resolution strategies. Pag naa ko’y problema sa mga teachers tungod sa ilang dili maayo nga mga attitude, nagapaningkamot gyud ko na maresolve ang conflict right away by talking to them privately”

(I overcame issues by utilizing conflict-resolution strategies. When I had problems with teachers due to their undesirable attitudes, I tried to resolve the conflict by talking to them privately.)

IDI-01 also added:

“so that’s it, I manage it by utilizing conflict-resolution strategies every time nga naa ko’y kasakit or kalibog sa situation. For example katong last time naay nag reklamo nga parents kay gipasakitan daw iyang anak sa isa ka teacher so I applied conflict resolution strategies og na found out nako nga nagbuhat buhat ra diay og storya ang bata”

(I managed it by utilizing conflict-resolution strategies every time I faced difficulties or confusion in a situation. For example, there was a time when a parent complained that a teacher hurt their child, so I applied conflict-resolution strategies and found out that the child had just made up a story)

In summary, the school heads emphasized the importance of emotional enrichment and resilience building in their leadership roles. They shared how they cultivated resilience during challenging times, such as personal crises and the COVID-19 pandemic, and practiced transparency by keeping their teams informed about institutional issues and decisions.

Fostering Open Communication

Fostering open communication was a key focus for the school heads, as they recognized its importance in creating a positive and productive environment. They emphasized the need to reflect on emotions before making decisions and to provide thoughtful responses to foster understanding and collaboration.

IDI-06 highlighted the importance of reflecting on emotions before deciding, she shared:

“para sa akoo, naga reflect lang gyud ko sa akong emotions before deciding. Naga practice ko anang dapat dili ko mag decide dayon pag suko kaayo ko or even pag naa ko sa state nga happy kaayo ko”

(for me, I reflected on my emotions before making decisions. I practiced not deciding immediately when I was angry or even happy.)

In addition, IDI-07 also shared:

“I did reflection on my emotions before deciding kay naa gyud mga situation nga dili pwede mag decide ta og ura urada. As school head, pag problemado na gyud ko kaayo, mohawa sa ko kadali sa school, mangita kog lugar nga peaceful aron maka reflect gyud kog tarong before ko mag decide”

(I reflected on my emotions before deciding because there were situations where making immediate decisions was inappropriate. As a school head, when I was extremely troubled, I would temporarily leave the school and find a peaceful place to reflect appropriately before deciding.)

In the same vein, IDI-01 highlighted the importance of having thoughtful responses, she shared:

“in overcome challenges, mao to siya, nagahatag ralog thoughtful responses sa mga teachers. Maski gud makasala na sila, nagapaningkamot gihapon ko maging careful sa akong mga words og the way ko motubag sa ilaha para malikayan na dili sila masakitan”

(to overcome challenges, I provided thoughtful responses to the teachers. Even when they made mistakes, I still made an effort to be careful with my words and the way I responded to them in order to avoid hurting their feelings)

Similarly, IDI-09 added:

“yes, for me lang ha, naga practice ko anang thoughtful response kay if kabalo ta moplastar sa atong storya man gud mas peaceful ang conversation unya dili pud mosamot ang kahiubos sa teacher”

(yes, for me, I practiced giving thoughtful responses because if we knew how to phrase our words correctly, the conversation would be more peaceful, and it would prevent further embarrassment for the teacher)

IDI-06 also shared:

“engaging leadership training was part of my leadership kay through ana kay mas open ang teachers sa pag communicate and mas

updated pud sila sa school policies, the school decisions and changes”

(engaging in leadership training was part of my leadership approach because it made teachers more open to communication and kept them updated on school policies, decisions, and changes)

IDI-02 highlighted the need for embracing diversity and acceptance in dealing with different personalities, she shared:

“embracing diversity and acceptance was very important and because yung na nga, you are dealing with different personalities different experiences, different backgrounds and because of that, kailangan e accept mo talaga sila”

(embracing diversity and acceptance was very important because I dealt with different personalities, experiences, and backgrounds. Because of that, it was necessary to accept them truly)

IDI-09 also added:

“kailangan gyud nato og diversity and acceptance samot na if naa ta sa point nga judgemental kaayo ta sa uban. So mao to, as school head, ginalikayan gyud nako na, so instead nga mo critic ko deretso, I tried my best to embrace them as they are”

(we needed diversity and acceptance, especially if we found ourselves judgmental towards others. So, as a school head, I avoided that by trying my best to embrace them as they were instead of criticizing them directly)

The school heads emphasized the importance of reflecting on emotions before making decisions, with some taking time away from stressful situations to gain clarity. They also highlighted the value of providing thoughtful responses to teachers to avoid causing additional distress and engaged in leadership training to improve emotional management and communication.

Maintaining Self Composure and Optimism

Maintaining self-composure and optimism is crucial for effective leadership, especially in high-pressure environments. It involves managing emotions to prevent hurtful situations and fostering a positive atmosphere among team members. Staying composed during intense moments and finding time to relax, whether very happy or angry, are essential for sustaining balanced leadership and personal well-being.

IDI-05 highlighted the importance of managing emotions to prevent hurtful situations, she shared:

“I managed my emotions to prevent hurtful situations and I also individually call the attention of the teachers and then I listen to them. And I also discuss my side unya after ana kay reconciliation na. And nag ask pud kog apology for the damage because that's very important”

(I managed my emotions to prevent hurtful situations and called the attention of teacher individually, and listened to them. I discussed my side, and after that, we went through reconciliation. I also asked an apology for any damage caused, which was very important.)

IDI-02 also added:

“I managed my emotions to prevent hurtful situations and tatawagin ko talaga at kakausapin ko kasi I believe that is the best way to solve the problems especially when it comes to emotion, kasi pag emotion parang matagal siyang mawala”

(ah, let us say someone was upset or held a grudge. I managed my emotions to prevent hurtful situations and would call them in to talk because I believed that was the best way to resolve problems, especially when it came to emotions)

In the same vein, IDI-04 emphasized fostering positivity in her leadership, she shared:

“I also fostered positivity at the end of every activity and in that way mas nakita nako nga motivated ang mga teachers mosulod sa work unya mas kabalo sila mo handle sa ilang emotions kay ginapakita man nako nga dapat positive lang maski daghang mga dili nindot nga mga happenings sa life”

(I also fostered positivity at the end of every activity; in that way, I saw that the teachers were more motivated to come to work and better at handling their emotions. I showed them that we should stay positive despite the many unpleasant events in life)

In addition, IDI-06 shared:

“I fostered positivity labi na og lisoran na kaayo ko sa sitwasyon, so instead mo nga maging negative ko, akoo gyud gina practice to always think positively and it helped me a lot nga maging confident sa akong mga skills as a school head”

(I first fostered positivity, especially when I was struggling with a situation. Instead of becoming negative, I practiced always thinking positively, which helped me a lot in building confidence in my skills as a school head)

In connection, IDI-04 highlighted the importance of staying composed in high-pressure situations, she shared:

“so for me, I stayed composed in high-pressure situations, samot na if naay mga problems sa school, for example kay last time katong nag online modalities tungod sa calamities, naa gyud time nga maglagot ka sa teachers kay walay pakialam sa mga reports and ako

nga school head, na mention na didtoa sa GC so ulaw gyud kaau sa akong part. So instead masuko ko sa naka assigned nga teacher, I stayed composed para dili ko makapasakit og storya sa ilaha”

(so, I stayed composed in high-pressure situations, especially when there were problems at school. For example, during the online modalities, due to calamities, there were times when I was frustrated with teachers who were neglecting their reports. As the school head, I was mentioned in the group chat, which was quite embarrassing. Instead of getting angry at the assigned teacher, I remained composed to avoid speaking harshly to them)

In addition, IDI-04 shared:

“sa time nga suko na kaayo ko og feeling nako and burn out na kaayo ko, I stayed composed. Wala nako gina allow na e control ko sa akong kaugalingong emotions kay para dili maapektohan ang trabaho”

(I stayed composed when I was extremely angry and felt burnt out. I did not allow my emotions to control me so that they would not affect my work)

IDI-08 shared the importance of having time to relax in all circumstances, she said:

“pag feel nako nga ma burn-out nako, I find time to relax especially pag feeling very happy or mad. Kay ne experienced man gud nako nga dili gyud maayo padalos dalos ta sa atong actions pag happy ta kay naa pud na siya’y negative outcomes and then pag sobraan rapud ta kasuko, dili pud maayo”

(when I felt burnt out, I found time to relax, especially when I was very happy or angry. I experienced that acting impulsively when happy could also have negative outcomes, and being excessively angry was not good either)

IDI-10 also added:

“I find time to relax when feeling very happy or mad to manage my own emotions. First, kay moginhawa kog lawom and allow myself time to process the situation before reacting. Second, I try to reframe the situation in a more positive light, kanang mag-focus ra gyud ko sa potential solutions rather than dwelling on the problem”

(I found time to relax when feeling very happy or angry to manage my own emotions. First, I took deep breaths and allowed myself time to process the situation before reacting. Second, I tried to reframe the situation in a more positive light, focusing on potential solutions rather than dwelling on the problem)

The school heads emphasized the importance of managing emotions to prevent hurtful situations by addressing issues and seeking reconciliation when needed. They fostered positivity by maintaining an optimistic outlook and promoting motivation among their staff, even in challenging circumstances.

Reduced Stress and Enhanced Motivation

Reducing stress and enhancing motivation is crucial for effective leadership and a positive work environment. School heads mitigated stress through open communication, addressing issues proactively to prevent escalation. They practiced self-reflection to manage their stress levels and fostered compassion towards their staff, creating a supportive atmosphere that encouraged motivation and well-being.

IDI-04 emphasized the need for open communication among every member at school, she shared:

“I mitigated stress through open communication among every member of the school and nakita pud nato nga ang teachers, parents, and learner’s kay free to expressed themselves para mas molambo pa atong school”

(I mitigated stress through open communication among every member of the school, and we also observed that teachers, parents, and learners were free to express themselves, which helped improve our school)

IDI-10 also added:

“So I mitigated stress through open communication sa teacher and after ato nakakita rapud kog solution sa problem by getting support from our PSDS and from the Division office, advising me on what to do in order to help the teacher”

(I mitigated the stress through open communication with the teacher, and afterward, I found a solution by seeking support from our PSDS and the Division office, who advised me on how to assist the teacher)

In the same vein, IDI-01 emphasized the importance of self-reflection to reduce the stress:

“so that’s it, I manage it by self-reflection para ma reduced ang stress, so everytime nga maglisod ko unsaon pag solve sa problem, ingana ra gyud akong ginabuhay”

(I managed it through self-reflection to reduce stress. Whenever I struggled with how to solve a problem, that was exactly what I did)

IDI-06 added:

"naga self-reflect ko para mas ma handle nko og tarong ang stress and also mas nakasabot pud ko sa akong goal, my aim, my objective as school head and it guided me also to do what is right."

(I engaged in self-reflection to better handle stress and understand my goals, aims, and objectives as a school head. It guided me in making the right decisions.)

In addition, IDI-05 emphasized the importance of compassion in building relationships, she shared:

"as a school head, naga hatag gyud kog compassion sa uban and dako siya og help sa pag built og healthy relationship sa tanan and also mas na maintain nako ang positive relationship because having a harmonious relationship based on the trust and respect, as I believed kay maka help na sa atoa in leading the school with a good relationship with the staff and students which affects the performance of the school"

(as a school head, I extended compassion to others, which significantly helped build healthy relationships with everyone. It also helped me maintain positive relationships, as I believed a harmonious relationship based on trust and respect was crucial. This, in turn, contributed to leading the school effectively with good relationships with the staff and students, positively affecting the school's performance)

IDI-02 also added:

"in every time that I have made a meeting, the first part of my message talaga is to foster a compassion with others kay gina encouraged nako ang teachers nga mas e love pa nila ang mga bata og ilang work by being compassionate"

(in every meeting I held, the first part of my message was to foster compassion towards others. I encouraged the teachers to love the children and their work even more by being compassionate)

The school heads highlighted several key strategies for reducing stress and enhancing motivation. They emphasized that open communication was crucial in managing stress and resolving issues, as it allowed for free expression among teachers, parents, and learners. They practiced self-reflection to handle stress better and align with their goals while fostering compassion to build and maintain positive relationships within the school community.

Insights of School Heads in Managing Emotion as they Lead their Schools

In response to the third question, "What insights on emotional management can school heads share with others?" most participants offered their ideas, advice, and perspectives on managing emotions while leading their schools. They emphasized their effective practices, leadership styles, and approaches that could help others dealing with similar challenges.

As participants shared their insights on emotional management, their responses revealed recurring themes in the transcriptions. During the data analysis, three (3) themes emerged, namely: (1) Promote a Positive and Supportive Environment; (2) Build Relationships and Trust; and (3) Prioritize Self-Care and Growth.

Table 3 shows the major themes and core ideas on the insights of school heads in managing emotion as they lead their schools.

Table 3. Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Insights of School Heads in Managing Emotion as they Lead their Schools

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Promote a Positive and Supportive Environment	fostering a supportive culture promoting effective communication prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers emphasizing humility and service
Build Relationships and Trust	reflecting on experiences and learning humility leading by example and strengthening relationships enhancing critical thinking and fostering positivity building strong relationships and teamwork
Prioritize Self-Care and Growth	balancing self-care employing commitment and humility prioritizing professional development for employee well-being

Promote a Positive and Supportive Environment

Supportive and inclusive leadership is vital for creating a thriving school environment. By fostering a supportive culture and promoting effective communication, leaders ensure everyone feels valued and heard. Prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers and emphasizing humility and service further strengthens the community, leading to a more cohesive and motivated team.

IDI-01 highlighted the need to foster a supportive culture within the school environment, she shared:

“fostering a supportive culture within a school environment can significantly enhance the overall well-being and performance of both teachers and students”

(fostering a supportive culture within a school environment significantly enhanced the overall well-being and performance of teachers and students)

IDI-02 also added:

“for future school heads, they need to show teachers a supportive culture kay para mas ma feel nila nga accepted sila and that they are given the chance to improve themselves without judgements”

(for future school heads they needed to show teachers a supportive culture so that they felt accepted and were given the chance to improve themselves without judgments)

In addition, IDI-03 highlighted the importance of effective communication to the success of the school:

“promoting effective communication is the backbone of a well-functioning educational institution. If school head know how to establish clear channels for communication between administration, teachers, students, and parents’ kay maka help na siya para ang tanan is on the same page, dili magka gubot ang decisions”

(promoting effective communication was the backbone of a well-functioning educational institution. If the school head knew how to establish clear channels for communication between administration, teachers, students, and parents, it helped ensure that everyone was on the same page and prevented confusion in decisions)

Similarly, IDI-04 added:

“they need to promote effective communication where teachers feel comfortable sa pag voice out sa ilang opinions and suggestions which will lead to more effective and efficient practices”

(they need to promote effective communication where teachers felt comfortable voicing their opinions and suggestions, which led to more effective and efficient practices)

Furthermore, IDI-05 highlighted the need to prioritize the emotional well-being of teachers, she shared:

“prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers is importante para ma maintain ang positive and productive school environment. School heads will be able to be prioritized emotional well-being for teachers by providing them mental health resources, such as counseling services or stress management workshops”

(prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers was important to maintain a positive and productive school environment. School heads prioritized the emotional well-being of teachers by providing them with mental health resources, such as counseling services or stress management workshops)

IDI-07 highlighted the importance of humility and service within the school community, she shared:

“para sa akoo, kailangan ma master sa mga future school heads ang act of humility and service within the school community para naay mutual respect and collaboration among teachers.”

(for me, future school heads needed to master the act of humility and service within the school community to foster mutual respect and collaboration among teachers)

IDI-08 also added:

“promoting humility and service kay it means kabalo sila mo value sa contributions of all members within school community. For example, they also need to celebrate acts of kindness and service, whether big or small, para mas ma inspired pa sila mo participate”

(promoting humility and service meant they knew how to value the contributions of all members within the school community. For example, they also needed to celebrate acts of kindness and service, whether big or small, to further inspire participation)

In summary, school heads must foster a supportive culture within schools to enhance the well-being of teachers and students. They shared that effective communication among school heads was essential for creating a healthy school environment. They also emphasized that prioritizing emotional well-being through mental health resources and work-life balance with demonstrating humility and service was crucial for fostering mutual respect and collaboration among staff.

Build Relationships and Trust

School heads shared that building relationships and trust within a school environment are essential for creating a collaborative and effective educational setting. They highlighted that reflecting on experiences, learning humility, leading by example, and strengthening relationships could build a foundation of mutual respect and trust.

IDI-01 emphasized the importance of reflecting on experiences and learning humility, she shared:

“reflecting on experiences and learning humility is one way nga mapakita nato ang sincerity sa atong pag served. If kabalo ta mo reflect sa atong mga experiences, mas maka help na siya para maging positive pa ang relationships and trust sa kaubanang teachers”

(reflecting on experiences and learning humility was one way to demonstrate sincerity in our service. When we were able to reflect on our experiences, it helped foster more positive relationships and trust with our fellow teachers)

In addition, IDI-03 shared:

“through reflecting on experiences and learning humility, makatabang gyud siya kay dinhi man nako natun an to listen to other people. Kumbaga kung humble ka mas maging nindot man gud imong relationship with your colleagues, it will make your work lighter”

(through reflecting on experiences and learning humility, it really helped me to listen to other people. Essentially, when you were humble, it improved your relationship with colleagues, making your work lighter)

In the same vein, IDI-08 shared the need for leading by examples and strengthening relationships, she shared:

“through leading by example and strengthening relationship, it helps me improve my ability to think deeper and wider, mas naging easy and calm ko when confronted with problems. It also develops effective teachers and students because they can trust and rely on you”

(through leading by example and strengthening relationships, it helped me improve my ability to think more deeply and broadly, and I became more easygoing and calm when confronted with problems. It also developed effective teachers and students because they could trust and rely on me)

IDI-05 also added:

“dapat maging example ka sa tanan and you need to strengthen relationships with other school heads to be more flexible, open minded to whatever situation may happen and be sensitive and give support and work with love and commitment”

(you needed to be an example to everyone and strengthen relationships with other school heads to be more flexible and open-minded to any situation that might arise. You also needed to be sensitive, offer support, and work with love and commitment)

Furthermore, IDI-08 highlighted need to enhance critical thinking and fostering positivity, she shared:

“being a leader is difficult, yes, lisod man gyud na but we can find a way to make it easier mao ng need nato e enhance ang critical thinking and we also need to foster positivity para sa tanang activities sa school. If kabalo ta mag foster og positivity mas maka build na siya and maka create ta og ways for teachers to flourish so that we can create a healthy and stress-free environment”

(being a leader was difficult, yes, it was truly challenging, but we needed to find ways to make it easier. That’s why we needed to enhance our critical thinking and foster positivity in all school activities. By fostering positivity, we could build and create ways for teachers to flourish, leading to a healthier and stress-free environment)

IDI-04 also shared:

“dapat as future school head, they need to enhance their critical thinking and they also need to foster positivity para mas ma maximized nila ang ilang day at work. Sa ingani pud nga ways mas dali nlang sa school head nga maka foster and built a strong commitment with their work and their co-workers”

(as future school heads, they needed to enhance their critical thinking and foster positivity to maximize their workday. In this way, it became easier for school heads to foster and build a strong commitment to their work and their co-workers)

In addition, IDI-03 realized the importance of building strong relationships and teamwork, she shared:

“building strong relationships and teamwork kay maka-help siya in dealing with problematic situations, and also maka kita pud ta og with reasonable solutions, and we will be able to control the feelings or emotions instead of letting them to take control of us”

(building strong relationships and teamwork helped us deal with problematic situations and enabled us to find reasonable solutions. We were able to control our feelings or emotions instead of letting them take control of us)

IDI-10 also added:

“to promote emotional management among staff, school heads must build strong relationships and teamwork para makabalo sila mo consider sa situation sa ubang teachers, specially katong naay mga personal problems sa family or other aspects”

(to promote emotional management among staff, school heads needed to build strong relationships and teamwork so they could consider the situations of other teachers, especially those with personal problems in their family or other aspects)

In summary, school heads emphasized the importance of reflecting on experiences and learning humility to foster positive relationships

and trust within the school community. They highlighted that leading by example and strengthening relationships improved their problem-solving abilities and created an environment where teachers and students could rely on them.

Prioritize Self-Care and Growth

School heads highlighted that prioritizing self-care and growth among teachers is essential for creating a thriving and sustainable school environment. They shared that balancing self-care with professional responsibilities would allow teachers to maintain their well-being while fulfilling their commitments with dedication and humility.

IDI-04 emphasized the need for balancing self-care, she shared:

“dapat kabalo gyud ang school heads in balancing self-care that would recharge them to release all stressors, and everything will follow. So again, dapat healthy ilang huna-huna and body because these will lead to positive actions and emotions”

(school heads needed to know how to balance self-care to recharge and release all stressors, allowing everything else to follow. Their minds and bodies needed to be healthy because this led to positive actions and emotions)

In addition, IDI-10 also shared:

“dapat kabalo gyud sila mag balance og self-care para mas ma handle og tarong ilang kaugalingon. This will equip school heads with tools to identify and manage their own emotions, as well as how to support students in doing the same”

(they needed to know how to balance self-care to better handle themselves. This equipped school heads with tools to identify and manage their own emotions, as well as how to support students in doing the same)

In addition, IDI-10 highlighted the importance of commitment and humility in utilizing emotional management in leadership:

“ang pinakaimportante nga realization that I had about is to employ a commitment and humility in utilizing emotional management in leadership. If kabalo ta maging committed and humble, we can create a more positive and supportive environment for everyone. This, in turn, fosters better relationships, improved communication, and ultimately leads to a more successful school for all stakeholders”

(the most important realization that I had was to employ commitment and humility in utilizing emotional management in leadership. When we knew how to be committed and humble, we could create a more positive and supportive environment for everyone. This, in turn, fostered better relationships, improved communication, and ultimately led to a more successful school for all stakeholders)

Similarly, IDI-05 also shared:

“dapat maging example sila sa tanan and they need to employ a commitment and humility to be better in their job. Kay if humble sila, mas kabalo sila mosabot sa situation sa ilang mga kaubanang teachers, and this will help them become more positive”

(they needed to be an example to everyone and employ commitment and humility to be better in their job. When they were humble, they were better able to understand the situations of their fellow teachers, and this helped them become more positive)

In the same vein, IDI-10 highlighted the need for prioritizing professional development for employee well-being, she shared:

“para sa mga newly hired school heads, they need to prioritized professional development for employee well-being. Mas maka help ni siya aron makatabang sa mga teachers to identify their own emotional triggers and preferred coping mechanisms”

(for newly hired school heads, they needed to prioritize professional development for employee well-being. This helped teachers identify their own emotional triggers and preferred coping mechanisms)

IDI-05 also added:

“Kailangan sa mga future school heads na mag developed og professional development for employee well-being so that they will be able to provide emotional support that provides access to school guidance advocates who will guide them to strengthen their emotional management”

(future school heads needed to develop professional development programs for employee well-being so that they could provide emotional support, including access to school guidance advocates who would help strengthen emotional management).

In summary, school heads emphasized the importance of balancing self-care to effectively manage stress and maintain positive emotions, which was crucial for their overall well-being. They highlighted that commitment and humility were essential for creating a supportive environment, improving relationships, and enhancing communication within the school.

Discussion

The study aimed to determine the correlation between faculty trust, collaborative This section presents the discussions based on the findings from this phenomenological inquiry. It includes an analysis of the emergent themes, which are supported by related literature from various authors. Additionally, it addresses the implications for accounting practice and provides recommendations for future

research.

Lived Experiences of School Heads on Managing Emotion as They Lead their Schools

School heads who were selected as research participants in this study shared their lived experiences of managing their emotions while leading their schools. From the data gathered, the following five (5) themes emerged: (1) Managing Emotions in Difficult Situations; (2) Staying Positive to Enhance Morale and Happy Disposition; (3) Building Strong Relationships and Promoting Productivity; (4) Maintaining Open Communication; and (5) Inability to Handle Own Emotions.

Managing Emotions in Difficult Situations

In the face of challenging situations, managing emotions is crucial for effective leadership. During the interviews, participants discussed various strategies to achieve this. These methods enable school heads to remain objective in decision-making, regulate their emotions to achieve favorable outcomes in tense circumstances, and effectively handle diverse personalities. Furthermore, the insights highlight the significance of a high emotional quotient in managing anger and maintaining emotional control, ensuring a comfortable environment for everyone involved.

A study by Widyadari and Fitriani (2023) found that emotional regulation is crucial to leadership effectiveness. Leaders who manage their emotions well are more likely to enhance decision-making processes, cultivate a positive organizational climate, and improve team interpersonal relationships. Similarly, Yunus and Chaudhary (2023) explain that this capability is closely tied to emotional intelligence.

In addition, Roy (2023) found that leaders with high emotional intelligence are better at managing their emotions in social situations, leading to improved stress management, conflict resolution, and relationship satisfaction. Furthermore, Tyra et al. (2022) highlighted that emotional regulation strategies, such as cognitive change and acceptance, are commonly employed by teachers to manage their emotions in the classroom, underscoring the importance of emotional regulation across various professional settings.

Kiishi (2024) highlights the role of emotion regulation in leadership effectiveness, especially in high-stress environments where maintaining a calm and composed demeanor is essential. Emotional intelligence, which encompasses recognizing, understanding, and managing emotions and those of others, is a significant predictor of leadership effectiveness. Bhopal and Devi (2023) found that regulating emotions is crucial for leaders to connect emotionally with employees, fostering organizational success, growth, and sustainability. Studies have shown that emotion regulation strategies, such as cognitive reappraisal, can buffer the negative impact of stress on mental health, enabling leaders to maintain their effectiveness under pressure.

Furthermore, Gvedashvili (2023) found that effective conflict management involves active listening, open communication, and peaceful resolution strategies to create an inclusive environment and prevent misunderstandings. Nurhayati et al. (2022) revealed that composure is needed to de-escalate tense situations and foster a collaborative atmosphere. Conflict, though often viewed as unpleasant, can improve organizational effectiveness when appropriately managed.

Babatunde et al. (2022) agree that conflict management strategies are essential due to tensions between small and large companies, highlighting the need to consider psychological factors in conflict resolution. By embracing the REACH Principle—Respect, Empathy, Audibility, Clarity, and Humility—leaders can effectively address organizational conflicts, create a conducive work environment, and enhance team collaboration.

In addition, Walsh et al. (2024) emphasized that mindfulness practices play a crucial role in helping leaders maintain emotional balance and composure by fostering present-moment awareness and non-judgmental observation of thoughts and emotions. This practice reduces stress and enhances emotional regulation, essential for effective leadership. Additionally, Perera et al. (2024) highlighted that mindfulness enhances cognitive and emotional regulation, promoting ethical decision-making and mitigating cognitive biases, vital for maintaining composure in complex situations.

Staying Positive to Enhance Morale and Happy Disposition

Staying positive is essential for boosting morale and fostering a happy disposition within organizational settings. Most school heads enhance positivity by expressing appreciation and recognition, encouraging a joyful attitude toward their work, and acknowledging the valid reasons behind others' actions. They also reflect on their methods for finding alternative solutions and ensuring fair treatment and understanding, which collectively contribute to a more positive and motivated work environment.

A study by Karsim et al. (2023) found that optimistic attitudes and positive leadership style significantly impact morale and happiness within organizational settings. Leaders who demonstrate appreciation recognition, and promote a culture of serving others contribute to a positive work environment. In addition, Joaquim et al. (2023) found that fostering a positive social environment through effective social interactions and creating a conducive work environment is crucial for enhancing job satisfaction.

Similarly, Guslina (2023) revealed that positive organizational behavior, which focuses on enhancing self-efficacy and motivation, offers a fresh perspective on organizational behavior and human resource management. Grabarski et al. (2022) supported that these approaches emphasize cultivating positivity and supportive relationships within the workplace, ultimately contributing to greater

satisfaction, engagement, and overall organizational success.

Building Strong Relationships and Promoting Productivity

Building strong relationships and promoting productivity contributed to several strategies identified by school heads. These include designing effective solutions to address challenges, providing robust support for teachers to foster collaborative work environments, and actively sharing best practices while encouraging feedback. They also emphasized the need to foster empathy and professionalism among teachers and make informed decisions to resolve miscommunications, maintain positive relationships, and enhance overall productivity within educational settings.

Shebli (2023) agrees that effective leadership practices are crucial in building strong relationships and promoting productivity in educational settings. Tomlin (2023) explains that school leaders can reduce teacher turnover by ensuring job satisfaction, improving working conditions, providing mentorship, addressing disciplinary issues promptly, fostering collegial relationships, and offering adequate compensation and recognition to teachers.

Additionally, Perez and Banayo (2023) found that strong leadership practices, such as establishing mentor-mentee relationships, promoting cooperation, providing timely feedback, and supporting continuous professional development, significantly enhance teacher performance and service quality. Alfajaro and Alfajaro (2023) supported that by nurturing trusting and respectful relationships, empowering individuals, and fostering co-ownership in collaborations between researchers and school leaders, educational institutions can create environments that support sharing best practices and a culture of constructive feedback.

Maintaining Open Communication

School heads have emphasized that promoting collaboration and open communication is essential for effective school leadership. They actively foster a positive outlook to reduce stress, express emotions constructively, and listen to diverse perspectives, encouraging open communication among staff and stakeholders. They focus on building strong relationships with teachers and personnel, recognizing the critical role of engaged listening in creating a supportive and collaborative school environment.

Saysin and Dhammapissamai (2023) supported the above findings as they found that effective leadership styles, such as ensuring job satisfaction, improving working conditions, providing mentorship, addressing disciplinary issues promptly, fostering collegial relationships, and offering incentives and recognition to teachers, are crucial for building strong relationships with teachers. Additionally, Hasibuan and Andika (2023) agree that organizational culture, encompassing leadership, teamwork, and adaptability, significantly influences school effectiveness, with a positive correlation observed particularly in public elementary schools.

Furthermore, Kamińska (2022) found that implementing online self-training programs for teachers to enhance students' teamwork skills has improved both teacher learning outcomes and students' effective teamwork skills in secondary schools. Cohen et al. (2022) explain that by adopting these practices and programs, schools can bolster staff morale, elevate student outcomes, and cultivate a positive organizational climate, ultimately leading to increased effectiveness across educational institutions.

Inability to Handle Own Emotions

The inability to handle own emotions poses significant challenges in leadership. School heads often encounter difficulties when others do not fully understand their good intentions, struggle to adjust to individual differences, and struggle to balance authority and empathy. When teachers or community members are not open to dialogue, it can be emotionally draining for leaders who must navigate mixed emotions and barriers to open communication.

Toprak and Karakus (2023) emphasized that emotional management poses significant challenges for school leaders, impacting their effectiveness. The research underscores the critical role of emotion regulation in leadership, particularly evident in contexts such as managing crises like the COVID-19 pandemic and in Islamic leadership emphasizing empathy and socio-emotional sensitivity. Warren et al. (2022) found that effective emotion management is crucial for addressing prejudice and supporting marginalized groups.

Furthermore, Jackman-Ryan et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of emotional control in school leaders' efforts to enhance learning systems and foster cultural change within educational environments. Taufik and Istiarsono (2020) also found that mastering emotion regulation enables school leaders to navigate complexities, accommodate differences, and maintain a balanced approach of assertiveness and empathy in their leadership roles.

Coping Strategies in Facing the Challenges Encountered in Managing Emotion as They Lead their Schools

During interviews, school heads shared their coping strategies to manage emotions while leading their schools. They also shared how they address emotional challenges, maintain effective leadership, and foster positive organizational climates amidst varying demands and pressures.

From the data gathered, the following four (4) themes emerged, namely: (1) Emotional Enhancement and Resilience Building; (2) Fostering Open Communication; (3) Maintaining Self Composure and Optimism; and (4) Reduced Stress and Enhanced Motivation.

Emotional Enhancement and Resilience Building

Emotional enhancement and resilience building involve encouraging stakeholders to see challenges as opportunities for growth and development. School heads lead by example, showing how to approach difficulties with a positive mindset and emotional strength. This not only enhances individual well-being but also cultivates a resilient school community that can thrive despite adversity, ensuring a supportive and adaptable learning environment for everyone involved.

Hylen (2023) supported the idea that effective leadership in educational settings prioritizes cultivating resilience among stakeholders. School leaders are pivotal in fostering transparency, strengthening relationships, embracing diverse perspectives, and building trust within their school communities to cultivate a positive organizational climate. Pillay-Naidoo and Nel (2022) also agree that utilizing improved decision-making and conflict-resolution strategies and fostering open communication is critical for enhancing emotional management skills and promoting resilience.

Moreover, Lobo (2022) found that applying lessons learned from training sessions enhances these skills, creating supportive environments that boost trust, resilience, and overall organizational effectiveness in educational institutions. Manoharan et al. (2024) revealed that effective leadership is needed in solving the complexities and challenges faced by academic institutions, particularly in fostering resilience and a positive school culture. Solomon et al. (2023) highlighted that leaders who demonstrate emotional grit and a positive outlook play a pivotal role in enhancing the well-being of individuals within the institution, thereby contributing to a resilient environment where students and staff feel supported and valued.

Fostering Open Communication

Fostering open communication through transparency in decision-making builds trust among stakeholders and promotes a culture where everyone feels valued and heard. This openness facilitates the exchange of ideas and feedback, which is crucial for continuous improvement and innovation. School heads who practice transparency show their commitment to integrity and accountability, strengthening relationships and supporting a cohesive school community.

Moreover, Qaisar et al. (2023) emphasized that effective leadership in educational settings relies on fostering growth through open communication and adaptive decision-making, with a strong focus on emotional intelligence. They highlighted the benefits of prioritizing reflective practices over impulsive reactions, which promote thoughtful and effective responses. Similarly, Mendoza (2023) identified that leadership training aimed at enhancing emotional intelligence is crucial for supporting diversity, fostering acceptance, and promoting adaptability.

Furthermore, Qiu (2023) underscored the importance of accommodating diverse emotional needs, promoting open communication, and fostering understanding to build inclusivity and collaboration within schools. Montefalcon and Zamora (2024) revealed that relational transparency among school heads is positively correlated with proactive behavior from teachers, indicating that transparent leadership can lead to more engaged and motivated teaching staff.

In connection, Raouf et al. (2024) further demonstrated that administrative transparency aids in diagnosing and addressing organizational issues, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of school management. These insights collectively underscore the significance of fostering open communication to improve school leadership and organizational effectiveness.

Maintaining Self Composure and Optimism

Maintaining self-composure and optimism is essential for effective leadership and emotional regulation, as it helps individuals stay balanced and positive when navigating various challenges. This approach fosters a more inclusive and collaborative environment, allowing leaders to manage diverse personalities with grace and confidence. By maintaining composure and a positive mindset, leaders can make more informed decisions and effectively handle complex situations.

Kour and Ansari (2024) emphasize that maintaining self-composure and optimism is crucial for leaders to enhance their emotional intelligence (EI) and create a supportive atmosphere conducive to positive interactions and conflict resolution. Emotional intelligence involves recognizing, understanding, and managing both one's own emotions and those of others, which is essential for effective leadership and organizational success. Mualla (2024) suggests that leaders who integrate diverse perspectives can enrich their decision-making processes, leading to more innovative and well-rounded solutions. This approach not only improves communication and collaboration but also aids in resolving conflicts amicably, as understanding and empathy are key elements of EI.

In addition, Kaaria and Karemu (2024) highlight that emotional intelligence is vital for cultivating an inclusive and harmonious work environment by equipping leaders to handle complex interpersonal dynamics and diverse personalities. Dunne-Moses et al. (2023) further explain that emotional intelligence encompasses the ability to manage one's own emotions and those of others, crucial for fostering a multicultural and inclusive atmosphere. In connection, Roque and Ramos (2023) find that applying emotional intelligence throughout an organization enhances interpersonal relationships and facilitates the resolution of differing viewpoints, thereby strengthening the overall organizational culture.

Reduced Stress and Enhanced Motivation

Reduced stress and enhanced motivation are crucial for managing workplace problems effectively and fostering a positive organizational environment. Emotional intelligence (EI) supports these outcomes by helping school leaders navigate interpersonal

relationships and appreciate diverse perspectives. By leveraging EI, school leaders can better address conflicts and improve the overall organizational climate, leading to a more motivated and less stressed work environment.

Ningtyas (2024) emphasized that reducing stress and enhancing motivation in the workplace involves effective conflict-resolution strategies, with emotional intelligence (EI) playing a crucial role. EI helps employees integrate new information with existing processes, improving their ability to manage dysfunctional tasks, processes, and relationship conflicts, which supports organizational learning. Similarly, Luqman et al. (2024) noted that school principals who use collaborative approaches like coaching and mediation can resolve disputes over values, interests, and perceptions, thus fostering mutual understanding and reducing stress.

Additionally, Gupta and Prasad (2024) found that higher levels of EI are linked to more effective conflict resolution styles, as individuals with higher EI are better equipped to handle conflicts, leading to enhanced motivation and a more positive work environment. Avdeeva and Kuznetsov (2023) also highlighted that frequent use of conflict resolution strategies such as accommodation, avoidance, and compromise underscores the importance of EI in reducing stress and fostering a cooperative and motivated work atmosphere.

Insights of School Heads in Managing Emotion as they Lead their Schools

School heads shared various strategies for emotional regulation, building supportive relationships, and encouraging effective communication within their school communities. They highlighted how these strategies are crucial for maintaining a positive school climate and improving leadership effectiveness in the face of challenges. From the data analysis, three (3) key themes emerged, namely: (1) Promote a Positive and Supportive Environment; (2) Build Relationships and Trust; and (3) Prioritize Self-Care and Growth.

Promote a Positive and Supportive Environment

In promoting a positive and supportive environment, school heads prioritize fostering a supportive culture and guiding colleagues to lead their respective groups effectively. They emphasize role modeling and effective communication as essential in exemplifying empathy, active listening, and fostering open communication within their school communities. Additionally, they recognize the significance of prioritizing emotional well-being to cultivate a supportive and positive school environment, where effective decision-making, problem-solving, humility, and service are integral components of leadership effectiveness.

Volosnikova (2023) argued that supportive and inclusive leadership practices are widely recognized in educational literature as crucial for fostering positive school environments and enhancing organizational effectiveness. Research emphasizes that school heads play a pivotal role in fostering a supportive culture and guiding colleagues toward effective group leadership. Boutwell and Smith (2023) also found that effective communication, role modeling, empathy, and active listening are essential leadership components that promote open communication and trust within school communities.

In addition, Boubée et al. (2023) highlighted that prioritizing emotional well-being is crucial for creating a positive school climate, which supports effective decision-making and problem-solving and promotes humility and service-oriented leadership. Neves et al. (2023) revealed that these practices contribute to a supportive and inclusive environment and enhance collaboration and growth within educational settings.

Build Relationships and Trust

Building positive relationships and trust is foundational to effective leadership in educational settings. School heads prioritize reflecting on experiences, learning humility, and enhancing their leadership abilities to foster positive connections and strengthen relationships within their school communities. They emphasize enhancing critical thinking, promoting positivity, and deepening connections to enhance decision-making skills and foster collaboration, ultimately building strong teamwork and supportive relationships that contribute to a cohesive and productive school environment.

Laurel (2023) found that establishing trust and positive relationships in educational leadership is crucial for cultivating a supportive and thriving school environment. Research emphasizes that school leaders engage in continuous self-improvement practices and reflect on their experiences to enhance their leadership abilities. They promote critical thinking and positivity to strengthen decision-making skills and foster collaboration among staff and stakeholders. Dollentas et al. (2023) supported that leaders must also focus on improving communication skills, decision-making abilities, and support for professional development to create a positive learning environment and address challenges effectively.

Additionally, Abdallah (2023) found that fostering deep connections and promoting strong teamwork within the school community contributes to creating a unified school climate that nurtures trust, ultimately boosting organizational effectiveness and success. In connection, Baxter and Ehren (2023) explained that trust in leadership is an important element that underpins school improvement, with trusting relationships identified as key drivers of positive school cultures and successful educational outcomes.

Prioritize Self-Care and Growth

School heads who prioritize self-care and growth could actively balance their responsibilities by fostering a healthy mindset and integrating self-care practices into their routines. This approach enhances their effectiveness and well-being, setting a positive example

for their staff and students and underscoring the importance of self-care and personal growth in cultivating a thriving educational environment.

Subsequently, Pitas and Brobo (2024) revealed that school heads prioritizing self-care and personal growth can significantly enhance their effectiveness and well-being, setting a positive example for their staff and students. This approach is crucial in cultivating a thriving educational environment. Nazareno et al. (2024) emphasized that resilient leadership, such as caring for teachers, significantly impacts teachers' resiliency levels, suggesting that school heads who integrate self-care practices into their routines can foster a more resilient and supportive school culture. Additionally, Devanadera and Ching (2023) found that promoting a growth mindset among school heads positively correlates with improved job behavior, further underscoring the importance of personal development in leadership roles.

Kim and Jung (2022) revealed that self-care, personal growth, and self-reflection enhance school leaders' well-being and effectiveness. Similarly, Edith and Minja (2023) found that leaders often contend with significant stress from diverse sources, impacting their personal lives and professional roles. Female leaders, in particular, frequently face stress related to the well-being of others and interactions with staff. Yengkopiong (2023) advised that leaders may adopt various self-care practices encompassing cognitive, emotional, occupational, spiritual, and physical dimensions, focusing on occupational self-care and seeking social support.

Implication for Emotional Management Practice

Based on the findings of this phenomenological study, significant implications emerge for educational leadership and beyond. School heads shared their strategies for coping with emotional difficulties, emphasizing the importance of maintaining composure, practicing emotional intelligence, and fostering open communication to navigate diverse personalities and stressful situations effectively. They revealed that their approaches to emotional regulation included promoting positivity, demonstrating empathy, and encouraging constructive dialogue to create a supportive and inclusive school environment. Insights gathered from the study suggest that school heads can enhance their leadership effectiveness and school climate by embracing diverse perspectives, managing stress, and utilizing conflict-resolution strategies to maintain motivation and resilience among staff and students.

In addition, enhancing organizational support through mentorship programs, peer support groups, and tailored leadership development initiatives focused on emotional resilience is crucial. These initiatives can empower leaders to navigate challenges more effectively, particularly in high-pressure environments. Addressing gender disparities in stress management and leadership effectiveness is equally imperative. Organizations may implement policies that support school heads in balancing professional responsibilities with personal well-being, addressing specific challenges identified in the study.

These recommendations may be directed at educational institutions, organizational leaders, and human resources departments aiming to foster a supportive and effective leadership culture. By implementing strategies, organizations can cultivate emotionally intelligent school heads who contribute to positive organizational climates, enhance employee satisfaction, and drive overall organizational success. Fostering these practices improves leadership effectiveness and contributes to creating healthier, more productive work environments across diverse sectors.

Conclusion

Based on the insights gleaned from the study, there are several recommendations made for future researchers that can expand their understanding of emotional management in educational leadership:

Firstly, further exploration into emotional management strategies such as journaling and meditation will help regulate school heads' emotions in different challenging scenarios. Researchers may delve deeper into specific studies where emotional regulation proves particularly needed and effective.

Additionally, longitudinal studies may warrant observing how emotional management evolves among school heads. Such research may track the impact of sustained emotional regulation on organizational climate, leadership effectiveness, and long-term outcomes within educational settings. Also, comparative studies across different educational systems may further enrich this field by exploring how cultural contexts shape emotional management practices and leadership effectiveness among school heads in public versus private schools or across different divisions in Region XI.

Moreover, evaluating the effectiveness of emotional management training programs tailored for school heads may present an opportunity to measure how these interventions enhance emotional competence, leadership skills, and overall school climate. Furthermore, investigating the role of technology in emotional management practices among school heads, particularly in virtual environments, may offer insights into how digital tools influence leadership effectiveness and emotional well-being. Another important area for exploration is understanding teacher perspectives on how school heads' emotional management impacts their job satisfaction, well-being, and professional growth. Research in this area may illuminate how emotional support from leaders influences teacher retention, performance, and the overall school climate through surveys and focus group discussions.

Lastly, comparing emotional regulation strategies across different leadership roles within educational settings, such as school principals, district administrators, and other educational leaders, may deepen our understanding of how emotional demands vary across

organizational levels. By addressing these research recommendations, scholars may contribute significantly to enhancing our understanding of emotional management in educational leadership, fostering more effective leadership practices and positive organizational outcomes in schools. Conducting this research study has provided valuable insights into the essential aspects of educational leadership. This study has explored themes such as emotional regulation strategies, conflict management, fostering positivity, promoting collaboration, and the challenges associated with emotional management in leadership roles.

One of the challenges encountered during this study was ensuring a focused exploration within the scope of emotional management among school heads. The complexity of emotional differences in educational settings required careful investigation to capture the responses of school heads regarding how they regulate their emotions amidst different challenges and responsibilities. Additionally, accessing and interpreting personal experiences shared by participants posed certain limitations, as emotions can be subjective and context dependent.

However, these challenges were outweighed by the significant realizations and learnings gained from this research study. It became evident that effective emotional management is not merely a personal attribute but a crucial skill that influences organizational climate, teacher morale, and student outcomes. School heads who exhibit high emotional intelligence and employ effective emotional regulation strategies are better equipped to foster positive school environments, manage conflicts constructively, and promote collaborative relationships among stakeholders.

Moreover, the study underscored the importance of ongoing professional development in emotional competence for school leaders. Programs aimed at enhancing emotional intelligence and providing practical strategies for emotional regulation may prove instrumental in equipping leaders to navigate the complexities of educational leadership effectively.

Through this research journey, I have gained a deeper appreciation for the complexities of emotional management in educational leadership and the transformative potential of cultivating emotional intelligence. I hope this study will inspire further research and innovation in the field. While this study has provided valuable insights into emotional management among school heads, there remains ample opportunity for further exploration.

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